

THE PHILOSOPHICAL STUDY OF INTELLIGENCE, LIFE AND HUMANITY EVOLUTION

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Abstract

This philosophical article focuses on a new conceptual view on intelligence, living beings and human society evolution. The paper discusses the direction of life and intelligence evolution by structural levels as unicellular beings, multicellular beings and human societies. It identifies processes explaining life appearance and evolution on Earth. The article evaluates a prediction for Humanity's future that human activity could result in transformation of the Earth to the next structural level of life. The study proposes a natural explanation of many facts not explained yet, employing factual logic and system analysis. It does not relate to any religion!

Keywords: Intelligence evolution; Humanity Future; Life; Society; Evolution.

1. Introduction

The Oxford Reference (<https://www.oxfordreference.com/page/144>) states that philosophy encompasses the study the nature of reality, of knowledge, of morality, and of the relationship between the mind and the body. The hypothesis of descending type of structural life levels intelligence evolution called *The Hypothesis of Descending Mind* does not follow precisely current paradigm and may appear as speculative at first sight. However, many early stage hypotheses like “endosymbiosis” by L. Margulis need more time and research to verify them. Because of that, author is using emphasis like “it looks” and “it seems” to show needed study.

A researcher of the American Humane Association Nels Quevli presented the first study of cell intelligence in the book *Cell Intelligence* (Quevli, 1916). The most recent research is the book *The Sentient Cell* (Reber et al, 2024). This proposed article is about intelligence evolution streaming through structural levels of universe.

The interesting facts and ideas considered that rarely discussed:

- How could be explained the cells based life genesis?
- We humans are not holistic living beings, but communities of 30 trillion unicellular living beings in each human person, built by one initial human origin cell using own plan and tools;
- Our likes and dislikes, including mating partners, in general, programmed by initial human origin cell being;

- If we follow current paradigm, separate female and male are not living beings, because they could not reproduce and only family including female and male appears a living being;
- Why multicellular life started to appear?
- Is stratification of society natural for humans?
- Why do human communities behave not as wisely as smart persons do?
- Are offensive wars natural?
- What would be the Humanity future?

The author realized several applied projects and published papers on a theory and practical implementation of intellect modeling. The second step appeared the intelligence evolution study described in this paper. The author does not believe in supernatural beings, and the *Hypothesis of Descending Mind* in no way connected with any religion.

The methods used are factual logic and systems analysis. Factual logic applied to study reliable facts from all branches of science to establish interconnection between them and to find general regularities. Systems analysis used to study complexity and internal structure of investigated entities.

2. The Hypothesis

Merriam-Webster dictionary defines intelligence as the ability to learn or understand or to deal with new or trying situations and to apply knowledge to manipulate one's environment (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/intelligence>). Margulis L. and Sagan C. state: "Not just animals are conscious but every organized being is conscious. In the simplest sense, consciousness is an awareness (has knowledge) of the outside world" (Trewavas and Baluška, 2011). Evolution hypothesis/theory proposed by famous scientist Charles Darwin is based on the assumption that intelligence is not involved in life building, and complex systems appeared because of undirected activities. The logic of this approach leads to the thought that intelligence is just one of ordinary features of living beings, having restricted impact on our future. It looks like old belief in inevitable fate appeared in many religions, describing people as slaves and toys of unknown mighty forces ruling the world.

We humans have now the following choices:

- Humans are primarily consumers and destroyers, just ordinary species struggling for life, and, in this case, human civilization will extinct due to destruction of environment historically very quickly;
- Humans are primarily creators and builders, and, in this case, human civilization will survive, controlled by united human intellect.

Every one of us does this choice of our future consciously or unconsciously.

Atom model developer Niels Bohr said that physics is not about how the world is; it is about what we can say about the world. Haw Yang, measuring with Liwei Lin the temperature of cells, pointed out at a meeting of the American Chemical Society in

2011 (American Chemical Society 2011) that the inside of a cell is so complicated, and we know very little about it. Étienne Danchin, Arnaud Pocheville and Philippe Huneman (2019) suggest that RNA emerges as a major, and overlooked, inheritance molecule, complementing and interacting with the DNA. Reber AS, Baluska F, and Miller W (2024) describe the biomolecular processes responsible for cellular consciousness in detail.

It seems we should be sure in our knowledge of complex objects only in a case we design them directly.

We know that human origin cells are able to build us using non-organic and simple organic parts. The one cell with dimensions up to 0.1 millimeter holds all the plan and needed tools to build human body containing about 30 trillion cells. As an example, if a human should do this work, the resulting being would cover an area with dimensions of 10,000 km*3,000 km and includes 30 trillion humans.

The complexity of an entity could be estimated by a number of parts in a system and richness of interactions. As shown by Robert A. Freitas (Freitas R. A., 1999), the typical human cell contains about 20 billion ~50,000-daltons (protons/neutrons) protein molecules of ~5,000 types, about 50 million ~1,000,000-daltons RNA molecules and 46 of ~100,000,000,000-daltons DNA molecules. Total number of molecules in a cell is about 100 trillion with a combined weight over 4,000 trillion daltons.

The common definition of life by Merriam-Webster dictionary (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/life>) is an organismic state characterized by capacity for metabolism, growth, reaction to stimuli and reproduction. All these qualities should have control points and direction to be successful, i.e. require intelligence. Only imagine that all it goes in a stochastic way!

The Stanford's human genome ENCODE project shows that only 1.5% of DNA are protein-coding genes and the main part of DNA controls functions of cell regulating expression of genes. There is also a pool of sleeping neutral elements waiting to be used (Stanford University, 2017). The DNA is carrying instructions used in the development and functioning of living cell, and in some sense acts similarly to a human brain that controls functions and all activities.

The author of this paper proposes to estimate human intellectual and instrumental abilities simply as not enough progressive to understand overall complexity of the world, and it is a cause of the fact that science is always looking unfinished. The humans are designers themselves, but objects created by humans are relatively simple compared with already existing atoms, cells and DNA.

2.1. *About life genesis*

It should be noted that all living beings are trying to be stable, but as a rule increase entropy/disorder in the outer world.

It is known that living beings are built by living beings of lesser or same size. Some cells produce the same cells by division process and some egg cells produce

multicellular beings by development of very complex structure beings. However, if we look down to the lesser size living objects the question arises - who had created them? Who was the creator of first cells?

We could think of the following possibilities.

- Living beings are built by living beings lesser or same size;
- All objects with a stable (structure)/(internal state) are living beings or controlled/created by living beings, because stability is provided by anti-entropy activity.

If we are prolonging previous thoughts it can be suggested that lesser parts of cells e.g. molecules, atoms and so on could be living beings themselves. In this case, we could explain physical and chemical interactions as activities of living beings. Please take into account that any object controlled by living beings, like a spaceship with astronauts, from an external point of view might look alive.

It is proposed to call an agent developing living being Living Being Engineering Authority – LBEA.

Humans are designed and built by much lesser beings, probably smarter than we are. It is evident that these LBEA are cells producing us. We are built to be universe/habitat for them, providing a safe environment. The homeostasis, the ability of keeping stability in a part of the universe occupied by living being, is obvious feature of life.

We humans are not the smartest living beings. Bigger does not mean smarter. If you can destroy living being it does not mean you are smarter. It means that you can act as a predator. However, if you can develop and build this living being, you are smarter indeed. Our attempt to modify genetically living beings is an imitation of viruses' activities.

Famous scientist Charles Darwin tried to explain advances in living beings by analogy of domestic species selection by humans. It is suggested in this article to consider, as analogy of life evolution, design and building tools, machines and societies by humans.

We are built to have a possibility to be LBEA that means that we can design and build new living beings. We build these beings the way cells build us, as a set of specialized humans. These beings are called families, tribes, cities, states, planets and so on. However, the structure looks similar: science, culture, government, energy production, healthcare, communication, transportation, reproduction, goods and food production, distribution, consumption and evacuation, defense facilities. It seems that humans are built with a structure like that too.

Darwinian evolution by natural selection is present in a certain sense among the living beings, whose design improved keeping most successful. We humans also improve design of societies and machines we build to reach the best results. Of course, the external world has influence on evolution promoting needed changes, but humans fulfill the real research, design and building.

Living being is built to keep safe environment for internal LBEA research, development and production. LBEA builds bigger being to include outside world area into that being. Goal of humans as LBEA should be to build living being including our planet Earth and so on.

And try to look for LBEA on different levels of the universe.

2.2. *The Physics*

It is interesting that known physicists follow old Greek tradition stating “Nothing exists except atoms and empty space.”

Brian Greene states: “standard model views the elementary constituents of the universe as point-like ingredients with no internal structure...” (Greene B, 1999)

The physicists say that physical particles communicate using messenger particles. Brian Greene said that “Messenger Particles... An electromagnetic field is composed of a swarm of photons; the interaction between two charged particles actually arises from their "shooting" photons back and forth between themselves...For like-charged particles, the photon carries the message "move apart," while for oppositely charged particles it carries the message "come together.” (Greene B, 1999)

We should imagine that point-like ordinary particles design, build, instruct and send point-like messenger particles to tell the world about exact position and intentions of the original particle. In addition, particles in the entire world should react to these messages. It seems that particles behave quite intelligently. It would be reasonable to suppose that they are very complex and powerful.

Quantum mechanics states that space is not so empty place as it looks. It would be right to suppose that non-existing nothing can produce only nothing. If a space produces virtual particles, it should have power to do this work. There is no strict distinction between real and virtual particles, because, if virtual particle exists for a long time, it is a real particle.

We observe that our universe is organized in an explicitly smart way.

Brian Greene states: “the universe would be a vastly different place if the properties of the matter and force particles were even moderately changed...” (Greene B, 1999)

Goal of LBEA is to keep stable space inside a living being, governed by special laws. Building own universe with unique physics is required. It would be said that if there is a law – it probably looks as set by intellect of LBEA.

Our goal as obvious micro-world predators is to find ways to use energy conserved on that scale, because we need energy for our own LBEA activity.

It is evident that energy could be acquired primarily by absorption and destruction of stable objects, in order to get energy saved during their building and life.

The smallest stable particles we observe directly are photons, neutrinos, electrons, neutrons and protons. Photons are taking part in electrons and protons creation. Neutrinos participate in protons-neutrons conversion. Protons, neutrons and electrons take

part in creation of atoms, the first is hydrogen. Probably, it could be estimated as LBEA activity.

It is supposed that conversion of massless photons into massive particles starts in very hot conditions as temperature 10^{13} K for protons/neutrons and 10^{10} K for electrons. After that a gas was cooling down, but particles remained.

We observe that photons start to form stable electrons and protons when temperature becomes lower than initially, but high enough to do this building. It could mean that they are trying to develop safe environment as a bit of previous state of the universe.

And protons, neutrons and electrons start to form stable atoms when temperature becomes even lower, but still relatively high. It might indicate that they are trying to develop atoms to exist inside in safety.

It looks like that new stable objects development starts in a case of external temperature/energy becoming lower, but high enough to supply energy for building.

Protons and electrons are known for their ability to form stable atoms of hydrogen. Hydrogen takes part in creation of complex atoms in a process called nucleosynthesis. Neutrons secure stability of nuclei. It looks like LBEA activity.

It is amazing that carbon, nitrogen and oxygen, known as vital in biology, actively take part in nucleosynthesis – chemical elements development inside stars in the CNO catalytic cycle occurring at 15 million K temperatures.

2.3. *The Chemistry*

Element carbon shows extraordinary creative abilities building structures of unlimited size like diamonds, graphite, grapheme, carbon nanotubes and all biological molecules.

Oxygen also shows very good creative abilities forming compounds with most elements. Nitrogen is demonstrating stabilization abilities being unreactive at standard temperature and pressure. Phosphorus has creative abilities having high reactivity.

Some elements as catalysts can control chemical reactivity that looks like intelligent activity.

2.4. *The Micro-Biology*

As stated in the book *Molecular Biology of the Cell* (Alberts B et al, 2002) “Living organisms...are made of only a small selection of these elements, four of which—carbon (C), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), and oxygen (O)—make up 96.5% of an organism's weight...Water accounts for about 70% of a cell's weight, and most intracellular reactions occur in an aqueous environment. Life on Earth began in the ocean...therefore hinges on the properties of water...If we disregard water, nearly all the molecules in a cell are based on carbon. Carbon is outstanding among all the elements in its ability to...generate large and complex molecules with no obvious upper limit to their size.”

The age of the Earth is about 4.5 billion years. The earliest life on Earth arose at least 3.5 billion years ago after sufficient crust had solidified, following the molten Hadean Eon with appearance of oceans.

And again it looks that life had appeared on Earth in a period of temperature decline though it stayed high enough to supply energy for development of living beings. It is supposed that possible reason for very complex carbon-based molecules development was desire to build safe environment for carbon atoms.

2.5. *The Biology*

The second step during further cooling of Earth was creation of the first unicellular species like simple bacteria/archaea called Last Universal Common Ancestor (LUCA), which appeared in several hundred million years after Earth became stable.

The most universal carbon-based molecules capable of playing LBEA's role in building of bacteria are RNA. Proteins are simpler and look like versatile machines designed to perform different functions, because they exist only for a limited period and then are recycled.

The different types of RNA cooperate to build objects, including RNA themselves, inside a cell. Some tRNAs are finding and transporting building parts, mRNAs supply instructions on what is to be built, and rRNAs build them directly. They obviously show intellectual functions of goals defining, exchanging information, supplies and complex building.

As stated in the book *Molecular Biology of the Cell* "All organic molecules are synthesized from and are broken down into the same set of simple compounds. Both their synthesis and their breakdown occur through sequences of chemical changes that are limited in scope and follow definite rules...The most fundamental role of nucleotides in the cell, however, is in the storage and retrieval of biological information...Proteins are especially abundant and versatile. They perform thousands of distinct functions in cells. Many proteins serve as enzymes, the catalysts that direct the large number of covalent bond-making and bond-breaking reactions." (Alberts B et al, 2002)

It is noted in the paper *The physiology and habitat of the last universal common ancestor* that Last Universal Common Ancestor of living beings probably inhabited environment like anaerobic hydrothermal vents/hot springs rich in H₂, CO₂ and iron. (Weiss MC et al, 2016)

It is stated by H. Follmann and C. Brownson (Follmann H, 2009) that Carbon fixation via iron-sulfur chemistry occurs at neutral pH and 100°C, and Iron-sulfur surfaces near hydrothermal vents are capable of producing some amino acids.

It was found by E. L. Shock that energy is maximized at around 100°C, the temperature at which some bacteria and archaea were found. (Shock EL, 1997)

It is shown in the paper by Mulkidjanian and colleagues *Origin of first cells at terrestrial, anoxic geothermal field* (Mulkidjanian AY et al, 2012) that the primordial

atmospheric pressure was about 100 atmospheres and UV irradiation was up to 100 times more intense than now, also they noted that blood and lymph resemble seawater, and not modern seawater, but water near geothermal fields, with atmosphere that oxygen depleted, CO²-dominated.

The sequence of life building could be the following. RNA communities for millions years lived inside lipid-like heat-insulating spheres where the environment was favorable for them. Some communities of RNA evolved to be large, not fitted inside these little spheres. They started to divide the spheres to replicate initial cells. They developed great plans for building new cells by members of the community with special abilities of replications plans development and keeping, looking like the first DNA. After the appearance of DNA, the possibility to build the same houses became real and we had initial point for cellular life evolution.

And we are not observing life development now primarily because the environment is absolutely different. Even if we model ancient environment, it could take millions years for carbon-based LBEA to design and build structures like first cells. Would we wait for it?

It was supposed that a great part of living being DNA is non-coding, but it is unlikely that this part does not play role for being. It should be proposed that this part performs functions of living being control, DNA research and development and contains alternative beings plans and samples of new patterns not finished yet. The point is that development of new features and even beings goes inside living being. Thus until development is finished, the previous integrity should be kept. The development can last for many years and generations, as shown in Richard Lenski *E. coli* long-term evolution experiment, and, until finished, external appearance and internal activities of being should not change significantly. And this way we have sudden appearance of new types or features of species after design is finished actually.

“The *E. coli* long-term evolution experiment is an ongoing study in experimental evolution led by Richard Lenski...The researchers concluded that the evolution of the Cit⁺ trait suggests that new traits evolve through three stages: potentiation (making the trait possible); actualization, (making the trait manifest); and refinement (making the trait effective)” (Blount ZD et al, 2012)

S. J. Gould said in his book *The Panda's Thumb* “The history of most fossil species includes two features particularly inconsistent with gradualism: 1. Stasis. Most species exhibit no directional change during their tenure on earth. They appear in the fossil record looking much the same as when they disappear; morphological change is usually limited and directionless. 2. Sudden appearance. In any local area, a species does not arise gradually by the steady transformation of its ancestors; it appears all at once and 'fully formed'.” (Gould SJ, 1980)

Genome building is parallel in a number of beings, so in a one moment many beings of an enhanced type should be born simultaneously.

For billions of years unicellular organisms were very successful developed fantastic variety of species. To provide fast speed of species development unicellular LBEA

probably developed two versions of beings – bacteria-like and viruses-like. Xin Hou et al (2024) say that evolutionary history of RNA viruses is at least as long that of the cellular organisms. Bacteria can advance DNA, but with slow speed. Viruses were specialized to develop new features for species at expense of having no ability to produce designed being. That's why all cellular organisms have the common base of DNA, but viruses contain more structural genomic diversity than plants, animals, archaea and bacteria. They are looking not like predators, as it's supposed, because predators don't kill themselves to attack any being.

By the way, multicellular beings as humans use this old method – males produce virus-like sperm cells and females produce bacteria-like egg cells.

Dr. C. Zimmer said in his article that “All cellular species, from E. coli to fin whales, have a core set of genes in common. Viruses, on the other hand, have no such universal set of genes...Some researchers have estimated that they (viruses) kill up to 40 percent of all bacteria in the ocean every day. Paradoxically, though, this daily massacre could actually increase the biomass of the oceans.” (Zimmer C, 2012)

It should be supposed that these viral attacks look like a reproduction type called semelparity, because the single reproductive event of semelparous organisms like salmon is usually fatal. Xin Hou et al (2024) say – “evolutionary history of RNA viruses is at least as long, if not longer, than that of the cellular organisms”. Viruses and virus-like elements encoded by the host are assisting horizontal gene transfer between species. It could mean that the advancement of species to provide a safer place is more valuable for LBEA than keeping existing ones. And it would prove that reproduction is needed not by species themselves, but by their LBEA.

Joshua S. Weitz and Steven W. Wilhelm said in their article that “...a liter of sea-water collected in marine surface waters typically contains at least 10 billion microbes and 100 billion viruses... viruses are certainly not limited to a single host genotype, nor to a particular species, and perhaps not even to a genus!..Finally, under certain conditions, a virus may become a long-term resident in its host cell, integrating its genomic material into that of its host to form a “lysogen.”” (Weitz JS and Wilhelm SW, 2013)

Bacteria inhabit soil, water, acidic hot springs, radioactive waste, and the deep portions of Earth's crust. Bacteria LBEA show extreme creative abilities, not surpassed by anyone. As noted by S. Redfern in his article “...bacteria, reproducing only once every 10,000 years, have been found in rocks 2.5km (1.5 miles) below the ocean floor that are as much as 100 million years old. Viruses and fungi have also been found...the microbes exist in very low concentrations, of around 1,000 microbes in every tea spoon full of rock... viruses are even more abundant, outnumbering microbes by more than 10 to one, with that ratio increasing with depth.” (Redfern S, 2013)

2.6. *The Zoology*

The multicellular beings started to appear widely after three events: gradual atmosphere oxygenation, eukaryotes appearance and several phases of glaciations. Oxygenation supplies more energy for beings. The last common ancestor of eukaryotes lived around 1.8 billion years ago. It looks that eukaryotes have much stronger control point provided by nucleus and it allows eukaryotes to produce multicellular living beings. Around 800 million years ago, there was a notable increase in the complexity and number of eukaryotes species in the fossil record. During the Cryogenian period, including Sturtian and Marinoan glaciations lasted from 720 to 635 million years ago, the oldest known fossils of animals appeared. Gradual glaciations, covering all the Earth and reaching equator, probably promotes unicellular beings to build greater beings to live inside in comfort. Greater beings are also capable to become predators for micro-beings thus having rich resources for living. After environment became life-friendly, multicellular organisms occupy all the Earth. Independence from outer temperature, intelligence development and social behavior lead to superiority.

2.7. *The Humanity*

The history of Humanity in a common sense began during last glacial period of Pleistocene lasting from 110,000 years ago until about 15,000 years ago.

The population geneticist Carlos Bustamante stated that his team now calculates that humanity's most recent common male ancestor (MRCA) lived 120,000 to 156,000 years ago. Bustamante's lab also reassessed humanity's maternal ancestry, calculating that the female MRCA lived 99,000 to 148,000 years ago. (Callaway E, 2013)

Humanity is only one type of hominids that able to be LBEA with brain designed in a unique way. In this humans can be comparable to Carbon and Eukaryotes capable of building stable structures of unlimited size. We become humans due to heredity and only in presence of human society around.

And the paper *Relaxed genetic control of cortical organization in human brains compared with chimpanzees* states that "A major result of increased plasticity is that the development of neural circuits that underlie behavior is shaped by the environmental, social, and cultural context more intensively in humans than in other primate species, thus providing an anatomical basis for behavioral and cognitive evolution." (Gómez-Robles A et al, 2015)

It is stated in a paper *The Anthropocene is functionally and stratigraphically distinct from the Holocene* "A January 2016 paper in Science investigating climatic, biological, and geochemical signatures of human activity in sediments and ice cores suggested the era since the mid-20th century should be recognised as a distinct geological epoch from the Holocene...The human impact on biodiversity forms one of the primary attributes of the Anthropocene...Human predation was noted as being unique in the history of life on Earth as being a globally distributed 'superpredator',

with predation of the adults of other apex predators and with widespread impacts on food webs worldwide..." (Waters CN et al, 2016)

2.8. *The Human Society*

The human culture began to flourish probably 50,000 years ago. The decisive role was played by ability of effective cooperation fixed genetically. Though features of aggressiveness and domination inside society are present in some persons, they may be treated as pre-modern-humans traits. They are recessive traits that observed in a few percents of humans.

"The modern human behaviors of technological innovation, making art and rapid cultural exchange probably came at the same time that we developed a more cooperative temperament," said lead author Robert Cieri. (Chieri R, 2014)

Our distant relative Chimpanzee has social hierarchy wherein more than one individual may dominate, even violently, over other members to get privileges.

But our closest relative Bonobo shows much gentler temperament. Leading evolutionary biologist Jeremy Griffith suggests that bonobos may be a living example of our distant human ancestors (Griffith J, 2013). The brain anatomy of bonobos has more developed and larger regions assumed to be vital for feeling empathy, sensing distress in others and feeling anxiety as pointed by Brian Vastag. (Vastag B, 2011)

Dictatorships and criminal gangs have social structures resembling Chimpanzee society, and democratic states look like Bonobo group.

John Gowdy writes: "Assumptions about human behaviour that members of market societies believe to be universal, that humans are naturally competitive and acquisitive, and that social stratification is natural, do not apply to many hunter-gatherer peoples...Anthropologists identify egalitarian cultures as "kinship-oriented," because they appear to value social harmony more than wealth or status...Kinship-oriented cultures actively work to prevent social hierarchies from developing because they believe that such stratification could lead to conflict and instability..." (Gowdy J, 2011)

As M. Shostak notes, the oldest known human society observed at South-African San tribes traditionally is an egalitarian one. The San made decisions among themselves by consensus, with women treated as equals. San were the most genetically diverse of any living humans studied that hints at the origin of anatomically modern humans. (Shostak M, 1983). We should suppose that social stratification is not natural for human communities and initially did not exist. Their consensus voting is much more effective than majority voting, because decisions approved by the wisest persons.

In our history the movement towards urbanization began around 7000 years ago during the Ubaid Period [5000 B.C.– 4000 B.C.] in Mesopotamia. In the paper *A Tale of Two Oikumenei: Variation in the Expansionary Dynamics of Ubaid and Uruk Mesopotamia* it is noted that "A contextual analysis comparing different regions

shows that the Ubaid expansion took place largely through the peaceful spread of an ideology". (Stein, G.J. and Özbal R. 2006)

As stated by G. Algaze, the rapid advancement of human civilization started with cities development during the Uruk period (ca. 4000 to 3100 BC) in Mesopotamia. The early city-states had strong signs of government organization and personal specialization, but social stratification was not evident until period around 3100 BC beginning with invasion of East Semitic Kish kings. (Algaze, G. 1993). It looks that during first two thousand years until external Kish invasion Mesopotamian civilization evolved peacefully. We should note that Mesopotamian civilization in many aspects is an ancestor of European one.

2.9. *The Human Future*

At the moment the possibilities for Humanity to exploit external areas on Earth are absent. The inertia of expansion has led us to the critical point.

William Ruddiman (Ruddiman, W.F. 2003) suggested that the Anthropocene began approximately 8,000 years ago with the development of stable agriculture and wave of extinctions, beginning with large mammals and land birds, driven by hunting and the consequences of land-use change for agriculture.

As stated by a non-profit organization Globaia: "A period marked by a regime change in the activity of industrial societies which began at the turn of the nineteenth century and which has caused global disruptions in the Earth System on a scale unprecedented in history: climate change, biodiversity loss, pollution of the sea, land and air, resources depredation, land cover denudation, radical transformation of the ecumene, among others. These changes command a major realignment of our consciousness and worldviews, and call for different ways to inhabit the Earth." (Globaia. 2017. Cartography of the Anthropocene, 2017)

As written by Clive Cookson in Financial Times, the risks of Humanity disappearing includes: *Artificial intelligence, Ecological collapse, Bad global governance, Global system collapse, Nuclear war, Global pandemic, Synthetic biology* and *Nanotechnology*. All these reasons are controllable by intellect and only absence of desire to use it could lead Humanity to extinction. Reasons like *Asteroid impact, Supervolcano* and *Extreme climate change* require evolution of science and technologies that also depends on intellectual efforts. (Cookson, C. 2015)

It should be noted that the rise of humans was supported by united Humanity intellect and it would be very strange not to use this now.

As written in the article *World faces 'perfect storm' of problems by 2030, chief scientist to warn* "A "perfect storm" of food shortages, scarce water and insufficient energy resources threaten to unleash public unrest, cross-border conflicts and mass migration as people flee from the worst-affected regions ... Our food reserves are at a 50-year low, but by 2030 we need to be producing 50% more food. At the same time, we will need 50% more energy, and 30% more fresh water... in some countries, al-

most half of all crops are lost to pests and disease before they are harvested. Substantial amounts of food are lost after harvesting, too, because of insufficient storage facilities.” (Sample, I. 2009)

Kate Lyons states that “Each year 1.3bn tonnes of food, about a third of all that is produced, is wasted, including about 45% of all fruit and vegetables, 35% of fish and seafood, 30% of cereals, 20% of dairy products and 20% of meat. Meanwhile, 795 million people suffer from severe hunger and malnutrition...If the amount of food wasted around the world were reduced by just 25% there would be enough food to feed all the people who are malnourished, according to the UN.” (Lyons, K. 2015)

Why the Humanity, featured from all species by great cooperative intellectual ability, use this ability ineffectively?

The Humanity history consists of two significant parts: civilization building with evolution/revolution and external military invasions destroying that built. The cities promote great achievements due to high concentration of talented people, organization, specialization and effective spreading of information and products. The stratification as well as slavery institution appeared probably due to foreign invaders/slaveholders setting themselves as superior over ordinary people. However, it does not mean that they were superior intellectually; they destroy/parasitize on a civilization as a rule.

Interestingly, there are two inconsistent views on a civilization.

First view describes civilization as a complex society characterized by urban development, social stratification, symbolic communication forms and a perceived separation from and domination over the natural environment. It is associated with the development of state structures, in which power was further monopolized by an elite ruling class who practiced human sacrifice. This way the Thousand-Year Reich with concentration camps by Adolf Hitler should be a higher point of civilization.

The second view describes civilization as the progress of Humanity as a whole, i.e. technological and cultural transition spreading new approaches to science and law around the world. Aided by division of labor and central government presence, civilizations have presented achievements in the arts, and countless new advances in science and technology.

Our history shows that the more stratification the more ineffective state, as it is described in HANDY Project. (Motesharrei, S. et al. 2017)

The human as a rule does not destroy own house and garden, so why Humanity destroys own house?

The reason is that society cannot be wiser than its leaders. Immoral leaders to justify their immorality propagate the idea that human civilization is based on stratification, competition and violence. The societies led by such leaders become stupid, dangerous and destructive, as we observe from cases of tyranny of different kinds. Usually these societies are not stable, like Nazi Germany, as an example.

The defensive wars are natural for human society, because even small beings, like bees, defend their home, at times killing aggressive species. The offensive wars are

unnatural, started as a rule by psychopathic leaders. However, even those psychopaths are trying to present offensive wars as defensive ones.

As written by prison psychologist and U.S. Army Captain Gustave M. Gilbert about ideas told him by one of the Nazi leaders H. Göring in Nuremberg: “Naturally, the common people don't want war; neither in Russia nor in England nor in America, nor for that matter in Germany...But, after all, it is the leaders of the country who determine the policy and it is always a simple matter to drag the people along, whether it is a democracy or a fascist dictatorship or a Parliament or a Communist dictatorship...All you have to do is tell them they are being attacked and denounce the pacifists for lack of patriotism and exposing the country to danger. It works the same way in any country... Hermann Göring, April 18, 1946.” (Villahermosa, G. 2006)

The study shows that immorality as a pre-modern-human trait is defined genetically in a very low number of people, probably not more than two percents. However, these people occupy high positions in human society due to lack of internal bans on immoral behavior. They are doing what modern people never do to get power and privileges.

Susan Krauss Whitbourne writes: “Defined as a set of traits that include the tendency to seek admiration and special treatment (otherwise known as narcissism), to be callous and insensitive (psychopathy) and to manipulate others (Machiavellianism), the Dark Triad is rapidly becoming a new focus of personality psychology. Researchers are finding that the Dark Triad underlies a host of undesirable behaviors including aggressiveness, sexual opportunism, and impulsivity“ (Whitbourne, S.K. 2013)

People of dark triad are more likely to commit crimes, cause social distress and create severe problems being in a leadership position. All traits of the dark triad have been found to have strong genetic components. It should be no surprise then that those at the top in high managerial positions are more likely to have narcissistic, psychopathic and Machiavellian tendencies. “...statistics: One in a hundred regular people is a psychopath...Although that figure rises to four percent of CEOs and business leaders,” according to British researcher Jon Ronson. (Ronson, J. 2012)

Practically all war criminals committed mass murders like Attila, Genghis Khan, Timur, Hitler, Tojo, Stalin and Putin – psychopaths of dark triad.

“...there are multiple paths to greatness and success in life. Many reach the top by being conspicuously caring — demonstrating a lifelong dedication to their broader communities and to helping others in their social worlds. Think Mother Theresa. On the other hand, there are relatively dark ways to reach the top in nearly all human social contexts...Displaying characteristics of the Dark Triad — being uncaring about others, self-absorbed, and manipulative — for better or worse, seems to also be an effective route to the top. It may not be a nice approach to social life, but it can be a successful one — particularly if others in the community allow this kind of strategy to succeed.” (Geher, G. 2016)

Global Wealth Report 2017 by Credit Suisse tells that the top 1 % of people alone accounts for half of total household wealth, primarily financial assets. (The Credit Suisse Research Institute, Global Wealth Report, 2017)

According to UN expert Juan Pablo Bohoslavsky, countries lose hundreds of billions of dollars every year (offshore), while individuals manage to hide between \$7 and \$25 trillion of funds that could and should be used to fund public services such as health care, schools, housing, social security, law enforcement, transportation infrastructure, and courts. (Bohoslavsky, J.P. 2016)

There are many persons of dark triad among billionaires. In reality, they dictate where global funds invested. The results are obvious – many technologies and products are harmful to humans and environment, but generate profits. They do not care about Humanity survival and future, only about their own gain, power and exclusivity.

It is not surprising that leaders of dark triad kind cannot be suitable leaders for human communities. It is very dangerous to delegate to such people great power in politics and economy, because they are psychopathic persons. They could be very successful working independently as scientists, artists, researchers, and under strict control in organizations like police and army. It is very risky to allow dark triad people occupy leadership positions and their own hierarchical organizations. It looks that future of Humanity depends on how this problem finds a solution.

Through history humans developed many types of societies called tribes, cities, countries and now global village. The sound ground for societies building is called morality – a genetically defined feature of the most modern humans. Marc Bekoff and Jessica Pierce (Bekoff, M. and Pierce, J. 2009) have thought that morality is a suite of interrelated other-regarding behaviors including empathy, reciprocity, altruism, cooperation and a sense of fairness that regulate complex interactions within social groups. Cognitive neuro-scientist Jean Decety (Decety, J. 2011) thinks that the ability to recognize and experience what another individual is feeling was a key step forward in the evolution of morality, and inability to feel empathy is one of the defining characteristics of psychopathy.

The modern-human type of leaders is moral and intellectual authority. People follow their rules due to moral and intellectual merits of these people, not being forced. We observe a need for this kind of leadership through all human history that means it is defined in modern humans genetically.

As Plato writes in his dialog Menexenus: “...our government was an aristocracy..., and is sometimes called democracy, but is really an aristocracy or government of the best which has the approval of the many;...but the natural equality of birth compels us to seek for legal equality, and to recognize no superiority except in the reputation of virtue and wisdom.” (Plato, Menexenus, 4th century B.C.)

The human evolution is not headed by hereditary ruling classes, and liberty, equality and fraternity are natural for majority of humans. The French Revolution in 1789 triggered the global decline of absolute monarchies replacing them with republics and

liberal democracies. The Revolution consisted in the suppression of the feudal system, in the emancipation of the individual, in greater division of landed property, the abolition of the privileges of noble birth, the establishment of equality including women and slaves.

The appearance of United Nations and Green parties defending principles of social justice, environmentalism and nonviolence, shows that Humanity LBEA activity begins to be visible globally.

In principle, there is interesting example of human state developed in a low resources area without any expansion, rated highly in the *Ranking of Happiness* due to scores of GDP per capita, social support, healthy life expectancy and freedom to make life choice. (WORLD HAPPINESS REPORT 2016, John Helliwell, Richard Layard, Jeffrey Sach, Eds., 2016)

As Graham Allison writes: "Singapore is today an ultra-modern metropolis of almost six million people with higher per capita GDP than the United States... Lee demanded of leaders both intellectual and moral superiority... Good government requires most of all leaders who put the public good unquestionably above their own personal interests... As he put it, the leader's objective was to "build up a society in which people will be rewarded not according to the amount of property they own, but according to their active contribution to society in physical or mental labor..." (Allison, G. 2015)

It should be noted that Singapore is a habitat built artificially to become stable. It looks that the whole Earth should be rearranged by Humanity into greater living being to secure its sustainability. And it is our work as LBEA.

2.10. *The Universe*

If we humans could build our Earth as a giant living being, the Earth may exist as independent spaceship. And from external view it should look like some type of black object, because it should be shielded and does not emit energy.

Our human civilization appeared in the Solar System which star Sun was born near the center of galaxy. It means that in early Universe human-like civilization would appear much more readily, because objects were significantly closer and space was richer with heavy elements.

The super-massive black holes of billions of solar masses have appeared very early in the Universe inside the first massive galaxies. Large fractions of the massive galaxies we now see around us were already formed just three billion years after the Big Bang as stated by European Southern Observatory (European Southern Observatory, 18 November 2015).

As stated in the paper *Water Formation During the Epoch of First Metal Enrichment* (2014): "Our results might have interesting implications for the question of how early could have life originated in the Universe". (Bialy, S. et al. 2014)

"Black holes have earned their fearsome reputation because any material – including stars – that falls within the so-called event horizon is never seen again. However, these new results indicate that the immense disks of gas known to orbit many black holes at a "safe" distance from the event horizon can help nurture the formation of new stars...there is a much higher percentage of massive stars in the disks around black holes. Moreover, when these massive stars explode as supernovae, they will "fertilize" the region with heavy elements such as oxygen. This may explain the large amounts of such elements observed in the disks of young supermassive black holes." (https://chandra.harvard.edu/press/05_releases/press_101305.html)

"A supermassive black hole heftier than 1 billion suns has been ejected from the core of its galaxy by gravitational waves, a new study suggests...The monster black hole has already zoomed 35,000 light-years away from its galaxy's center, farther than Earth and its sun are from the core of our own Milky Way...“We estimate that it took the equivalent energy of 100 million supernovae exploding simultaneously to jettison the black hole,” study co-author Stefano Bianchi, from Roma Tre University in Italy, said in a statement."

(<https://www.space.com/36187-gravitational-waves-boot-supermassive-black-hole.html>)

The objects known as super-massive black holes are looking not like super-heavy balls, but like extremely complex entities. Their origin is unknown. They are very small with mass only about 1/1000 of own galaxy, possessing volume comparable with Solar System and average density (defined as the mass of the black hole divided by the volume within its Schwarzschild radius) less than the density of water. However, they control all substantial activities in the own galaxies, including stars creation and supernova explosions supplying heavy elements needed for life. It is known that they could merge in a case of their galaxies are merging – how they could find common point in a huge galaxy space? They are surrounded by high temperature gas and thousands stars – why there is no giant explosion at their merging? Why they would prefer not to merge at times and second black hole starts moving outside a galaxy? They are behaving like intelligent entities. Is it possible that they are huge cities of billions years civilizations, and galaxies are their own yards and gardens?

3. The Conclusion

The hypothesis

- Life appears present at all the universe times, evolving through structural levels, like unicellular and multicellular living beings levels observed today;
- At every structural life level, living beings, called LBEA, build from own communities higher level living beings as a universe/habitat for their own safe activity in environment similar to environment of initial appearance of these beings;

- Because of that descending type of structural life levels intelligence evolution is present;
- Humans, like LBEA, have the ability to build big beings including unlimited number of persons, great areas and the planet itself, providing sustainable future of Humanity;
- The evolving planet size LBEA living being, like Humanity civilization, would have the ability to control big objects like galaxies and so on.

How to verify this hypothesis?

If a person could independently build living being with desired features from inorganic parts, it would prove that this wise person is as smart as human origin cells. All the Humanity would praise this person, because it would solve great existential problems like ability of full regeneration of cells and organisms at any age. Please note that DNA does not contain instructions how to build living beings from inorganic parts.

The ideas of these respected researchers are compatible with proposed hypothesis.

- Known biologist Masatoshi Nei has long maintained the view that the driving force of evolution is mutation and that natural selection is primarily a force eliminating less fit genotypes. He conducted statistical analyzes of evolution of genes and obtained evidence supporting this theory.
- James Alan Shapiro, lead author of the first team to isolate a single gene from an organism, has proposed the term natural genetic engineering to account for how novelty is created in the course of biological evolution. Shapiro maintains that many genome changes that occur naturally operate by similar molecular DNA rearrangements to those applied intentionally by scientists using genetic engineering techniques.
- Nels Quevli supposed in 1916 that cell intelligence is the cause of growth, heredity and instinctive actions, illustrating that the cell is a conscious, intelligent being, and, by reason thereof, plans and builds all plants and animals in the same manner that man constructs houses, railroads and other structures.
- British scientist J.B.S Haldane and Russian biochemist Aleksandr Oparin independently suggested idea that organic molecules could be formed from abiogenic materials in the presence of an external energy source.
- Klaas J. Hellingwerf (2005), Trewavas AJ and Baluška F (2011), Anthony Trewavas, (2014) tell that bacterial signal transduction — more than 50 signals have so far been identified — is controlled by a phosphoneural network in which changes in phosphorylation create or break network connections, thereby acting as logical operators. This process is analogous to changes in dendritic connections in the brain and it enables bacteria to make ‘informed decisions’. Autoamplification of parts of the network in response to environmental signals results in ‘learning behaviour’. Brains and nerve cells are not necessary for intelligent behavior. Organisms cannot rely alone on sim-

ple reflexes in complex environments; there is insufficient room in the genome for solutions for all to be encoded. Organisms learn from experience and apply that knowledge to future challenges. Learning is central to all intelligent behaviour. If reason is profiting from experience to modify current behaviour, then most organisms are capable of reason whether it be simple or complex.

- Étienne Danchin , Arnaud Pocheville and Philippe Huneman (2019) tell that while the second half of the twentieth century hyped the role of the DNA molecule, the RNA molecule is now confirmed as being another major molecule of inheritance, indeed encoding information over shorter terms than DNA, but still with effects spanning over many generations.
- Reber AS, Baluska F, and Miller W (2024) describe the biomolecular processes responsible for cellular consciousness in detail.
- The Noosphere is a philosophical concept developed and popularized by the biogeochemist Vladimir Vernadsky and philosopher Pierre Teilhard de Chardin. Vernadsky defined the Noosphere as the new state of the biosphere, and described it as the planetary "sphere of reason". The Noosphere represents the highest stage of biospheric development, that of humankind's rational activities.

Please note that the author studies evolution of human societies not for a presentation of political views, but because thinks that this study describes processes similar to those present in evolution of all living beings. By the way, if politics is natural phenomenon, should it have natural reasons?

The current biological paradigm promotes ideas about undirected evolution based on overall competition over resources. Humanity ability to consume and destroy resources appears so great that due to this paradigm we should extinct in historically little time. Would we try to find a paradigm promoting survival of Humanity?

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5. Declarations Introduction

5.1. Ethics Approval

Not applicable

5.2. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

5.3. Data Availability

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

5.4. Author Contribution

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5.6. Consent to publish

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